

Supplementary Material for Sensing Enhancement Design for MIMO-OFDM Integrated Sensing and Communication Systems With Subcarrier Allocation

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APPENDIX

A. Proof of Lemma 1

Let \mathbf{D} be Hermitian, $\mathbf{D} \succeq 0$, $\mathbf{L} \succeq 0$ and $k > 0$. To prove that for any point $\bar{\mathbf{t}}$ such that $\bar{\mathbf{t}}^H \mathbf{D} \bar{\mathbf{t}} > 0$ the function

$$u(\mathbf{t}; \bar{\mathbf{t}}) = -\frac{f(\bar{\mathbf{t}})^2}{\bar{\mathbf{t}}^H \mathbf{D} \bar{\mathbf{t}}} \left(\mathbf{t}^H \mathbf{L} \mathbf{t} + \frac{-2\Re\{\bar{\mathbf{t}}^H \mathbf{D} \mathbf{t}\}}{f(\bar{\mathbf{t}})} + k \right) \quad (\text{A1})$$

serves as a surrogate function for the objective function

$$f(\mathbf{t}) = (\mathbf{t}^H \mathbf{D} \mathbf{t}) (\mathbf{t}^H \mathbf{L} \mathbf{t} + k)^{-1} \quad (\text{A2})$$

in the Minorization-Maximization (MM) algorithm, two conditions must be satisfied [47]:

- *Equality Condition:* The surrogate function value equals the objective function value at the current point $\bar{\mathbf{t}}$, i.e.,

$$u(\bar{\mathbf{t}}; \bar{\mathbf{t}}) = f(\bar{\mathbf{t}}). \quad (\text{A3})$$

- *Lower Bound Condition:* The surrogate function is less than or equal to the objective function, i.e.,

$$u(\mathbf{t}; \bar{\mathbf{t}}) \leq f(\mathbf{t}), \quad \forall \mathbf{t}. \quad (\text{A4})$$

1) Verify the Equality Condition

Given $\bar{\mathbf{t}}$ such that $\bar{\mathbf{t}}^H \mathbf{D} \bar{\mathbf{t}} > 0$, and using the fact that $\Re\{\bar{\mathbf{t}}^H \mathbf{D} \bar{\mathbf{t}}\} = \bar{\mathbf{t}}^H \mathbf{D} \bar{\mathbf{t}}$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} u(\bar{\mathbf{t}}; \bar{\mathbf{t}}) &= -\frac{f(\bar{\mathbf{t}})^2}{\bar{\mathbf{t}}^H \mathbf{D} \bar{\mathbf{t}}} \left(\bar{\mathbf{t}}^H \mathbf{L} \bar{\mathbf{t}} + \frac{-2\bar{\mathbf{t}}^H \mathbf{D} \bar{\mathbf{t}}}{f(\bar{\mathbf{t}})} + k \right). \\ &= -\frac{f(\bar{\mathbf{t}})^2}{\bar{\mathbf{t}}^H \mathbf{D} \bar{\mathbf{t}}} \left(\frac{-2\bar{\mathbf{t}}^H \mathbf{D} \bar{\mathbf{t}}}{f(\bar{\mathbf{t}})} + \frac{\bar{\mathbf{t}}^H \mathbf{D} \bar{\mathbf{t}}}{f(\bar{\mathbf{t}})} \right). \\ &= f(\bar{\mathbf{t}}). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A5})$$

Thus, $u(\bar{\mathbf{t}}; \bar{\mathbf{t}})$ satisfies the equality condition.

2) Verify the Lower Bound Condition

To simplify the expression of the proof, let

$$\begin{cases} a = \mathbf{t}^H \mathbf{D} \mathbf{t}, \\ b = \mathbf{t}^H \mathbf{L} \mathbf{t} + k, \\ \bar{a} = \bar{\mathbf{t}}^H \mathbf{D} \bar{\mathbf{t}}, \\ \bar{b} = \bar{\mathbf{t}}^H \mathbf{L} \bar{\mathbf{t}} + k. \end{cases} \quad (\text{A6})$$

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Given that $\mathbf{D} \succeq 0$, $\bar{\mathbf{t}}^H \mathbf{D} \bar{\mathbf{t}} > 0$, $\mathbf{L} \succeq 0$, and $k > 0$, we have $a \geq 0$, $b > 0$, $\bar{a} > 0$, and $\bar{b} > 0$. We can then write $f(\bar{\mathbf{t}}) = \frac{\bar{a}}{\bar{b}}$, $f(\mathbf{t}) = \frac{a}{b}$, and the surrogate function is

$$u(\mathbf{t}; \bar{\mathbf{t}}) = -\frac{f(\bar{\mathbf{t}})^2}{\bar{a}} \left(\frac{-2\Re\{\bar{\mathbf{t}}^H \mathbf{D} \mathbf{t}\}}{f(\bar{\mathbf{t}})} + b \right). \quad (\text{A7})$$

We need to prove:

$$\frac{a}{b} + \frac{f(\bar{\mathbf{t}})^2}{\bar{a}} \left(\frac{-2\Re\{\bar{\mathbf{t}}^H \mathbf{D} \mathbf{t}\}}{f(\bar{\mathbf{t}})} + b \right) \geq 0, \quad \forall \mathbf{t}. \quad (\text{A8})$$

Since \mathbf{D} is Hermitian, it can be unitarily diagonalized; i.e., $\mathbf{D} = \mathbf{U} \mathbf{\Lambda} \mathbf{U}^H$, where \mathbf{U} is unitary and $\mathbf{\Lambda}$ is a real diagonal matrix. Given that $\mathbf{D} \succeq 0$, we define $\mathbf{Q} = \mathbf{\Lambda}^{1/2} \mathbf{U}^H$, which leads to the decomposition $\mathbf{D} = \mathbf{Q}^H \mathbf{Q}$. By the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality, for any two vectors \mathbf{o} and \mathbf{v} , it holds that $|\Re\{\mathbf{o}^H \mathbf{v}\}| \leq \|\mathbf{o}\| \|\mathbf{v}\|$. Let $\mathbf{o} = \mathbf{Q} \bar{\mathbf{t}}$ and $\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{t}$, the following inequality holds: $|\Re\{\bar{\mathbf{t}}^H \mathbf{D} \mathbf{t}\}| \leq \|\mathbf{Q} \bar{\mathbf{t}}\| \|\mathbf{Q} \mathbf{t}\|$. Consequently, the left-hand side of inequality (A8) satisfies:

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{a}{b} + \frac{f(\bar{\mathbf{t}})^2}{\bar{a}} \left(\frac{-2\Re\{\bar{\mathbf{t}}^H \mathbf{D} \mathbf{t}\}}{f(\bar{\mathbf{t}})} + b \right) \\ &= \frac{a}{b} - \frac{2f(\bar{\mathbf{t}}) \Re\{\bar{\mathbf{t}}^H \mathbf{Q}^H \mathbf{Q} \mathbf{t}\}}{\bar{a}} + \frac{f(\bar{\mathbf{t}})^2 b}{\bar{a}} \\ &\geq \frac{a}{b} - \frac{2f(\bar{\mathbf{t}}) \|\mathbf{Q} \bar{\mathbf{t}}\| \|\mathbf{Q} \mathbf{t}\|}{\|\mathbf{Q} \bar{\mathbf{t}}\|^2} + \frac{f(\bar{\mathbf{t}})^2 b}{\bar{a}} \\ &= \frac{a}{b} - \frac{2f(\bar{\mathbf{t}}) \|\mathbf{Q} \mathbf{t}\|}{\|\mathbf{Q} \bar{\mathbf{t}}\|} + \frac{f(\bar{\mathbf{t}})^2 b}{\bar{a}}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A9})$$

The Arithmetic Mean-Geometric Mean (AM-GM) inequality states that for $x, y \geq 0$, it holds that $x + y \geq 2\sqrt{xy}$. Setting $x = \frac{a}{b}$ and $y = \frac{f(\bar{\mathbf{t}})^2 b}{\bar{a}}$ yields:

$$\frac{a}{b} + \frac{f(\bar{\mathbf{t}})^2 b}{\bar{a}} \geq 2\sqrt{\frac{a}{b} \times \frac{f(\bar{\mathbf{t}})^2 b}{\bar{a}}} = 2f(\bar{\mathbf{t}}) \sqrt{\frac{\bar{a}}{a}}. \quad (\text{A10})$$

Meanwhile,

$$\frac{2f(\bar{\mathbf{t}}) \|\mathbf{Q} \mathbf{t}\|}{\|\mathbf{Q} \bar{\mathbf{t}}\|} = 2f(\bar{\mathbf{t}}) \sqrt{\frac{\|\mathbf{Q} \mathbf{t}\|^2}{\|\mathbf{Q} \bar{\mathbf{t}}\|^2}} = 2f(\bar{\mathbf{t}}) \sqrt{\frac{a}{\bar{a}}}. \quad (\text{A11})$$

Thus,

$$\frac{a}{b} - \frac{2f(\bar{\mathbf{t}}) \|\mathbf{Q} \mathbf{t}\|}{\|\mathbf{Q} \bar{\mathbf{t}}\|} + \frac{f(\bar{\mathbf{t}})^2 b}{\bar{a}} \geq 0, \quad (\text{A12})$$

which proves that inequality (A8) always holds, satisfying the lower-bound condition $u(\mathbf{t}; \bar{\mathbf{t}}) \leq f(\mathbf{t})$ for all \mathbf{t} .

In summary, since the surrogate function $u(\mathbf{t}; \bar{\mathbf{t}})$ satisfies the equality condition and the lower bound condition, it can serve as the surrogate function for the objective function in the MM algorithm. *Lemma 1* is thus proven.